

REPOPSI Start-Project Evaluation Using the RDA FAIR Data Maturity Model

Source

FAIR Data Maturity Model Working Group. (2020). FAIR Data Maturity Model. Specification and Guidelines (1.0). <https://doi.org/10.15497/rda00050>

About the Repository

REPOPSI is an open repository for psychological measures, scales, tests, and other research instruments in Serbian. It is maintained by researchers at the Laboratory for Research of Individual Differences (LIRA) at the Faculty of Philosophy, University of Belgrade. REPOPSI is hosted on the Open Science Framework (OSF) platform at <https://osf.io/5zb8p/>.

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This report was created as part of the project titled “TRUST-ification and FAIR-ification of an open repository for research instruments in psychology: REPOPSI's adoption of RDA outputs”, which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101017536.

The funding was awarded through the RDA (<https://www.rd-alliance.org/>) Open Call mechanism (<https://eoscfuture-grants.eu/provider/research-data-alliance>) based on evaluations of external, independent experts.

Evaluation Method

Measuring progress (for more details see *6.1 Measuring progress*, p. 34).

While “it is likely that FAIR practices can vary a lot from one community to another, eventually because their requirements can be different” (*3.4 Evaluation methods*, p. 10), we chose not to discard any of the indicators.

Evaluation by Indicator

F - Findable

F1 (F1-01M, F1-01D, F1-02M, F1-02D) - Metadata and data are identified by a persistent and globally unique identifier

METRIC - “4” - fully implemented

Explanation: For every metadata record and digital object that it describes (data) a globally unique identifier (GUID) is assigned. OSF is listed in the FAIRsharing registry service at <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.g4z879>. For every metadata record there is a Digital Object Identifier (DOI), minted by DataCite.

Read more on GUIDs on the OSF Support page, [Project and Components FAQ's](#), *What's a globally unique identifier (GUID)? What metadata is maintained about them?* question.

F2-01M - Rich metadata is provided to allow discovery

METRIC - “4” - fully implemented

Explanation: Description metadata is provided by OSF, which implements the DataCite Metadata Schema (source: <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.g4z879>). Additionally, every digital object (i.e. psychological instrument) is enriched with embedded metadata that further describes its provenance, citation, contributors, and provides instructions on how to use the digital resource.

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F3-01M - Metadata includes the identifier for the data

METRIC - “2” - under consideration or in planning phase

Explanation: The metadata is listed in the inventory files ([CSV](#) and [XLSX](#)) and a [Google spreadsheet](#) containing the identifiers of the data. The inventory files are located in the Files section, while the spreadsheet is linked in the Description field. However, there is no metadata element that explicitly connects to the data identifiers in a machine-readable way. This has to do with the limitations of OSF.

We will look for a better solution to include data identifiers in a more appropriate and machine-actionable way. One of the possible solutions would be to include the list of all identifiers in a Wiki page of each component.

Accessing all public data from metadata is possible via OSF’s open API (documentation is available at <https://developer.osf.io/>; an example of data retrieval from API is available at <https://api.osf.io/v2/nodes/f9mpd/files/osfstorage/>).

F4-01M - Metadata is offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed

METRIC - “4” - fully implemented

Explanation: All public metadata is easily accessed through the OSF API. Metadata are indexed in the Datasite, Crossref, Google Scholar, SHARE, Europe PMC, and Web of Science indexes (source: [How OSF Meets ‘Desirable Characteristics for Data Repositories’](#)).

A - Accessible

A1-01M - Metadata contains information to enable the user to get access to the data

METRIC - “4” - fully implemented

Explanation: Metadata contains all information to enable the user to access the data. The Repository follows an easily navigable scheme and access to data is straightforward.

A1-02M - Metadata can be accessed manually (i.e. with human intervention)

METRIC - “4” - fully implemented

Explanation: Visitors to the repository can access metadata through the user interface. All REPOPSI metadata is publicly available.

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A1-02D - Data can be accessed manually (i.e. with human intervention)

METRIC - "4" - fully implemented

Explanation: Visitors to the repository can access all the available data through the user interface. There is a user guide available on the REPOPSI Wiki page (<https://osf.io/5zb8p/wiki/home/>).

A1-03M - Metadata identifier resolves to a metadata record

METRIC - "4" - fully implemented

Explanation: All metadata records are enriched with a DOI that resolves to a metadata record.

A1-03D - Data identifier resolves to a digital object

METRIC - "4" - fully implemented

Explanation: All data objects are enriched with a GUID that is unique and permanent and that resolves to a designated digital object.

A1-04M - Metadata is accessed through standardised protocol

METRIC - "4" - fully implemented

Explanation: Repository metadata can be accessed through standardised protocols like HTTP. OSF also provides every necessary documentation on how to use the API for accessing the metadata.

A1-04M - Data is accessible through standardised protocol

METRIC - "4" - fully implemented

Explanation: Data can be accessed through the standardised HTTP protocol.

A1-05D - Data can be accessed automatically (i.e. by a computer program)

METRIC - "4" - fully implemented

Explanation: Data can be accessed through the OSF open API. OSF provides all necessary documentation on how to use the API at <https://developer.osf.io/>.

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A1.1-01M - Metadata is accessible through a free access protocol

METRIC - “4” - fully implemented

Explanation: Repository metadata can be accessed through the standardised HTTP protocol. This protocol is freely available and extensively used.

A1.1-01D - Data is accessible through a free access protocol

METRIC - “4” - fully implemented

Explanation: Repository data can be accessed through the standardised HTTP protocol. This protocol is the standard protocol for data exchange on the Internet and is freely available.

A1.2-01D - Data is accessible through an access protocol that supports authentication and authorisation

METRIC - “4” - fully implemented

Explanation: OSF supports authentication and authorisation. Specifically, it is possible to make OSF components private (source: [Control Your Privacy \(OSF Projects\) Settings](#)) and grant access to them on a user-to-user basis (source: [Grant Access to a Project \(OSF Projects\)](#)) At the moment, however, REPOPSI does not use this service since all data (psychological instruments) are open and available under a Creative Commons licence.

A2-01M - Metadata is guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available

METRIC - “4” - fully implemented

Explanation: OSF has a partnership with Internet Archive for long-term preservation with a \$250k preservation fund (source: <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.g4z879>). If a data file is deleted or withdrawn, the GUID will always resolve to a page that provides metadata about the removed file (file name, storage provider, if the deletion occurred on OSF or on an add-on service, name/GUID of user who deleted the file, and timestamp of file deletion). For deleted or withdrawn projects and components, and users a similar page will exist at that GUID noting that the content has been removed (source: [Project and Components FAQ's](#), *What's a globally unique identifier (GUID)? What metadata is maintained about them?* question).

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I - Interoperable

I1-01M - Metadata uses knowledge representation expressed in standardised format

METRIC - "2" - under consideration or in planning phase

Explanation: At the moment, metadata values are not expressed with any known controlled vocabulary or other standardised format. All metadata values are given in a form of a free text with the exception of timestamp which is generated automatically following the ISO 8601 standard. The usage of controlled vocabularies like the UNESCO Thesaurus (<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.81dc5f>) or the Library of Congress Subject Headings (<https://fairsharing.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.d31795>) as a way to standardise keywords is currently being considered.

I1-01D - Data uses knowledge representation expressed in standardised format

METRIC - "4" - fully implemented

Explanation: All files describing instruments are in PDF and ODT formats, which are very much in use within the target community (i.e. psychology researchers and students).

I1-02M - Metadata uses machine-understandable knowledge representation

METRIC - "4" - fully implemented

Explanation: Every metadata record has a permalink in the form of a DOI. These DOIs are minted by DataCite (source: [Project and Components FAQ's](#), *I have a project on OSF but searching the associated DOI on google doesn't bring up the page in results. Is the DOI active?* question), which automatically transforms metadata in a machine-understandable knowledge representation form like JSON-LD and Schema.org.

I1-02D - Data uses machine-understandable knowledge representation

METRIC - "1" - not being considered this yet

Explanation: Machine-understandable knowledge representation of data files is not being considered at the moment. Although all files in the Repository are in ODT format, which is part of an OpenDocument Format and based on an open standard (OpenOffice XML file specification), we do not believe that this can be seen as a form of a standardised knowledge representation.

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I2-01M - Metadata uses FAIR-compliant vocabularies

METRIC - "1" - not being considered this yet

Explanation: Since no controlled vocabularies are in use at the moment, as explained under I1-01M, this indicator has the lowest metric score.

I2-01D - Data uses FAIR-compliant vocabularies

METRIC - "1" - not being considered this yet

Explanation: Using controlled vocabularies for data is not under consideration at the moment.

I3-01M - Metadata includes references to other metadata

METRIC - "1" - not being considered this yet

Explanation: This is not under consideration at the moment.

I3-01D - Data includes references to other data

METRIC - "4" - fully implemented

Explanation: Currently, most of the data objects include references to other data in the form of a DOI pointing to a journal article or preprint, while some of the data objects also include a GUID pointing to where the authors additionally stored the psychological instrument on OSF, outside of REPOPSI.

I3-02M - Metadata includes references to other data

METRIC - "1" - not being considered yet

Explanation: This is not under consideration at the moment.

I3-02D - Data includes qualified references to other data

METRIC - "1" - not being considered yet

Explanation: This is not under consideration at the moment.

I3-03M - Metadata includes qualified references to other metadata

METRIC - "1" - not being considered yet

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Explanation: This is not under consideration at the moment.

I3-03D - Metadata includes qualified references to other data

METRIC - “1” - not being considered yet

Explanation: This is not under consideration at the moment.

R - Reusable

R1-01M - Plurality of accurate and relevant attributes are provided to allow reuse

METRIC - “4” - fully implemented

Explanation: Both metadata and data provide enough information to allow everybody to use it without any difficulties or ambiguities. Information about the versions of records is provided as well.

R1.1-01M - Metadata includes information about the licence under which the data can be reused

METRIC - “4” - fully implemented

Explanation: Every metadata record includes the information on the licence and terms of use. It is mostly in a human-readable form.

R1.1-02M - Metadata refers to a standard reuse licence

METRIC - “4” - fully implemented

Explanation: Every metadata record includes the information on the licence and terms of use. Metadata refers to a Creative Commons licence.

R1.1-03M - Metadata refers to a machine-understandable reuse licence

METRIC - “2” - under consideration or in planning phase

Explanation: All data is licensed under a Creative Commons BY-NC-SA licence. Since OSF does not provide an option to choose this kind of licence, there is no way to present it in a machine-readable format. We are considering other options to provide licence information in a machine-readable format.

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R1.2-01M - Metadata includes provenance information according to community-specific standards

METRIC - "4" - fully implemented

Explanation: All metadata have provenance information that is in accordance with the community-specific standards in the field of psychology (e.g., the scientific article where the original instrument or the instrument translation was first published, the names of the people who translated the instrument).

R1.2-01M - Metadata includes provenance information according to a cross-community language

METRIC - "4" - fully implemented

Explanation: All metadata have provenance information that is in accordance with the community-specific standards in the field of psychology (see under R1.2-01M). However, this language is straightforward and can be easily understood by academics from other fields (especially social sciences and humanities).

R1.3-01M - Metadata complies with a community standard

METRIC - "4" - fully implemented

Explanation: OSF implements DataCite Metadata Schema which is a generalised metadata schema (source: <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.g4z879>). Furthermore, each data file is enriched with embedded metadata that complies with the community-specific standards in the field of psychology.

R1.3-01D - Data complies with a community standard

METRIC - "4" - fully implemented

Explanation: All the data are in PDF and ODT formats, both well-known and well-used in the target community (i.e. psychology researchers and students).

R1.3-02M - Metadata is expressed in compliance with a machine-understandable community standard

METRIC - "4" - fully implemented

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Explanation: Metadata is expressed with DataCite Metadata Schema (source: <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.g4z879>), which has a machine-understandable standard that can be used in the target community.

R1.3-02D - Data is expressed in compliance with a machine-understandable community standard

METRIC - "4" - fully implemented

Explanation: Data is in PDF and ODT formats. PDF is a de-facto standard in many communities when it comes to textual documents. ODT is part of an OpenDocument Format and based on an open standard (OpenOffice XML file specification), which means that it is represented in a machine-understandable way.

Conclusion

This report is the result of a self-assessment test at the beginning of the project titled "TRUST-ification and FAIR-ification of an open repository for research instruments in psychology: REPOPSI's adoption of RDA outputs" (project team members: Aleksandra Lazić, Ljiljana Lazarević, Danka Purić, Iris Žeželj, Obrad Vučkovic). We will use this test to get a better idea on where to concentrate efforts to make REPOPSI resources more FAIR. We will conduct another self-assessment test at the end of the project in July 2023. Comparing the start- and end-project tests, we will evaluate the progress we made.

Figure 1 visualises the results of the evaluation of the indicators for all the FAIR areas. It was created using the spreadsheet provided by the FAIR Data Maturity Model Working Group, available at <https://doi.org/10.15497/rda00050>.

At the moment, REPOPSI has fully implemented the Accessibility principle. The areas of Findability and Reusability are also well developed, with only one indicator in each area requiring more work. Furthermore, some REPOPSI practices have the potential to be improved to achieve a higher level of Interoperability.

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Figure 1 FAIR Maturity Visualisation for REPOPSI

Note. Numbers refer to the five levels of compliance: 0 – not applicable; 1 – not being considered yet; 2 – under consideration or in planning phase; 3 – in implementation phase; 4 – fully implemented.

The only indicator for Findable that is not fully implemented (F3-01M) states that metadata should include the identifier for the data. Since OSF does not provide a metadata element associating metadata with the data by mentioning the globally unique and persistent identifier of the data, we plan to include the list of all data GUIDs in a Wiki page of each OSF component.

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The only indicator for Reusable that is not fully implemented (R1.1-03M) states that metadata needs to refer to a machine-understandable reuse licence. This is important as it would allow licences to be processed by machines, without human intervention. One barrier to meeting this requirement is that the list of licence types provided by OSF does not include the Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0 International (CC BY-NC-SA 4.0) licence, which is the one chosen for all of the REPOPSI contents. We plan to store a machine-readable licence as licence.txt in OSF components of the instruments. Alternatively, we could provide an XML version of the instruments with embedded machine-readable licence information.

The Interoperability principle has the lowest overall score, with most of the indicator maturity levels being either "1" (not being considered yet) or "2" (under consideration or in the planning phase). We will try to improve the Interoperability of the Repository, but it is important to note that, in doing so, we will have to comply with the limitations of the OSF platform. One of the indicators that can be improved (I1-01M) states that metadata should use knowledge representation expressed in a standardised format. To ensure better findability and interoperability, it is important to implement commonly used controlled vocabularies, ontologies or thesauri that follow the FAIR principles (i.e. that have resolvable globally unique and persistent identifiers). We plan to implement the UNESCO Thesaurus (<https://vocabularies.unesco.org/browser/thesaurus/en/>) or the Library of Congress Subject Headings (<https://id.loc.gov/authorities/subjects.html>). Both controlled vocabularies have machine-readable structures and are listed in the [FAIRsharing.org](https://fairsharing.org) registry as examples of FAIR controlled vocabularies.

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